

UNIVERSITET TALABALARINING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHI
KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada universitet talabalarining jismoniy rivojlanishi ko'rsatkichlari tahlili haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlarning jismoniy rivojlanishi akseleratsiya hodisasi, sport o'yinlari, chaqiriqqacha harbiy ta'lim, tana uzunligi va og'irligi, ko'krak qafasi aylanasi.

ANALYSIS OF INDICATORS OF THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF
UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Abstract. This article reflects on the analysis of indicators of the physical development of university students.

Keywords: the physical development of young people is an accelerating phenomenon, sports games, military education up to the call, body length and weight, chest circumference.

АНАЛИЗ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ
ВУЗОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается анализ показателей физического развития студентов вузов.

Ключевые слова: физическое развитие молодежи феномен ускорения, спортивные игры, военное обучение до призыва, длина и вес тела, обхват груди.

Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari, xalq ta'limi va o'rta maxsus o'quv yurtlari uchun turli sohalar bo'yicha mutaxassislar tayyorlash yo'nalishi mavjud gumanitar oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi o'quv jarayonini takomillashtirish ta'lim tizimining dolzarb pedagogik muammosi sanaladi. Shu sababli oliy gumanitar ta'lim muassasasida ta'lim oluvchi turli yo'nalishlar talabalarining butun to'rt yillik ta'lim sikli davomidagi jismoniy holatini o'rganish hamda tajriba tadqiqotlari davomida olingan raqamli axborotlarni qiyosiy tahlil etish asosida ilmiy-metodik tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish, ularni talabalarining harakat tayyorgarligini yanada takomillashtirish maqsadida o'quv jarayoniga joriy qilish katta qiziqish uyg'otdi.

Ma'lumki, so'nggi yillarda o'quvchi yoshlarning jismoniy rivojlanishi akseleratsiya hodisasi keng tarqalishi munosabati bilan ko'pgina tadqiqotchilar tomonidan ushbu muammo o'rganib kelinmoqda. Tadqiqotlardan aniqlanishicha, o'sib kelayotgan avlodning jadal rivojlanishi turli xil etnik guruhlarni qamrab olgan bo'lib, irsiy omillarga bog'liq emas, balki, asosan, tashqi muhit bilan o'zaro bog'liq. Tajriba tadqiqotlarini o'tkazish maqsadida chaqiriqqacha harbiy ta'lim fakultetida tahsil oluvchi talabalarining antropometrik tavsiflari - tana uzunligi va og'irligi, ko'krak qafasi aylanasi, o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imining o'zgarish dinamikasi hamda dinamometrik tavsiflari ta'lim yillari bo'yicha tadqiq qilindi. Olib borilgan tajriba tadqiqotlari natijalari 3.5-jadvalda berilgan.

Gavda uzunligi ko'rsatkichlari organizmning shakllanish xususiyatini aks ettiruvchi jismoniy rivojlanishning baholaydigan omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Birinchi bosqich talabalarida tana uzunligi o'rtacha $177,4 \pm 3,8$ sm.ni tashkil etadi, ikkinchi bosqich talabalarida farq $0,1$ sm.ni tashkil qiladi, uchinchi bosqichga kelib ko'rsatkich sezilarli pasayadi va farq $3,5$ sm.ni tashkil etadi va to'rtinchi bosqichga kelib $176,4 \pm 6$ sm.gacha o'sadi.

Vazn tavsiflarini baholay turib, o'quv yillari bo'yicha tana og'irligining oshib borishini e'tirof etish zarur. Agar birinchi bosqichda talabalarda tana og'irligi o'rtacha $74,1 \pm 1,0$ kg.ga teng bo'lgan bo'lsa, keyingi bosqichga o'tish bilan tana og'irligi 0,3 kg.ga oshdi, keyinchalik u $76,4 \pm 8,1$ kg.gacha o'sib bordi va birinchi bosqich talabalari vazniga nisbat 2,3 kg. farqni tashkil qildi. To'rtinchi bosqich talabalari o'rtacha 76 ± 7 kg. vaznga ega bo'ldilar, bu birinchi bosqich talabalari gavda og'irligidan 3,9 kg.ga ko'proq va bosqichdan-bosqichga talabalarning harakat faolligi kamayib borishidan dalolat beradi.

№	Ko'rsatkichlar	I bosqich			II bosqich			III bosqich			IV bosqich		
		\bar{X}	σ	V	\bar{X}	σ	V	\bar{X}	σ	V	\bar{X}	σ	V
1.	Bo'yi, sm	177,4	3,8	2,1	177,7	4,2	2,3	173,9	5,4	3,68	176,4	6	3,4
2.	Og'irligi kg	73,1	12,05	15,8	75,4	7,2	9,5	76	8,1	11	77	7	9
3.	Ko'krak qafasi aylanasi (naf.ol.), sm	98,8	6,7	6,5	93,8	7	7,1	96,9	4,6	4,5	99,3	4,3	4,1
4.	Nafas chiqarish, sm	91,1	8,3	8,8	88,5	5,8	6,3	91,2	5,9	6,2	91,8	4,9	5,1
5.	Dinamometriya o'ng, kg	43,6	6,8	14,5	45,2	4,9	10,1	47,3	9,6	19	45	5,6	11,7

6.	Dinamo- metriya chap, kg	40,4	8,3	19,1	44,6	7,8	16,5	44,9	9,01	18,8	416	5,1	11,5
7.	O'TS, ml	3560	310,5	8,5	4200	1016, 6	23,6	3360	287,0 5	8,3	3680	371, 5	9,8

Farg'ona davlat universiteti talabalarining jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlar

Universitet talabalarining o'quv yillari bo'yicha bo'y-vazn ko'rsatkichlari tahlili shuni aniqlab beradiki, ular to'rtinchi bosqichga qadar asta-sekin oshib boradi.

Universitet talabalarida o'quv yillari bo'yicha antropometrik ma'lumotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, asosan $r > 0,001$ da ko'rsatkichlarning barcha o'rganilayotgan parametrlar bo'yicha, asosan, ishonchsiz o'sishi va ayni paytda ikkinchi va uchinchi bosqichlarda ularning bir oz ishonchsiz pasayishi kuzatildi. Bu oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining an'anaviy jismoniy tarbiya tizimi kamchiliklari to'g'risida taxmin qilishga asos bo'la oladi.

Hozirgi zamon maktab o'quvchisi o'zining 85% vaqtini o'tirib o'tkazadi. U sinfdan – sinfga ko'chgan sari harakat faolligi so'zsiz pasayib boradi. Bu esa uning salomatligi va jismoniy rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bunday kamchilikni yo'qotish uchun bolalarni juda kichik yoshdan boshlab muntazam ravishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan mashg'ul qilish lozim.

Sport o'yinlaridan sport seksiyasi ishini takomillashtirish ham maktab o'quvchilarini yanada ko'proq mashg'ulotlarga jalb etishda vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Sport o'yinlari dunyoda keng taraqqiy etgan. Uning ommaviyligi shundaki, yoshlar va barcha mehnatkashlarni jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan sistemali shug'ullanishga, "Alpomish" va "Barchinoy" sinov me'yorlarini topshirishga va faol dam olishga vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Sport o'yinlari bilan shug'ullanish odam harakat apparatini rivojlantirishga imkoniyat yaratadi, hayotiy zarur bo'lgan chaqqonlik, chidamlilik, reaksiyani tezkorligi kabi sifatarni shakllanishga yordam beradi, nafas olish, yurak – qon tomir va muskul sistemalarini mustahkamlaydi, aqliy charchoqni yo'qotadi.

Sog'lomlashtirish – gigiena tomondan sport o'yinlari tarbiyaviy va targ'ibot-tashviqot jihatdan katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Sportcha kurash nafaqat ishtirok etuvchilarga, balki tomoshabinlarga ham maroqlidir. Bu kuchli bo'lishga intilish, chaqqonlik, jasurlik, o'z harakatlari bilan jamoaga aqliy yordam berish kabi sifatarni tarbiyalaydi.

Maktabda sport o'yinlari seksiyasini tuzish va mashg'ulotlarga ko'proq shug'ullanuvchilarni jalb etish uchun jismoniy madaniyat jamoasida bir qancha tadbirlarni o'tkazish kerak. O'quvchilar bilan o'tkazilgan biror bir kecha yoki umumiy yig'indan keyin voleybol, futbol, basketbol, qo'l to'pi, tennis, musobaqalari haqidagi (masalan, jahon chempionati) filmlarini yoki ko'rgazmalarni ko'rsatishdan boshlash mumkin. Shundan so'ng mamlakatimizning, viloyatning, shahar va tumanning taniqli murabbiylari bilan uchrashuv o'tkazishni yo'lga qo'yish kerak. Ular sport o'yinlari haqida, sport hayotidagi qiziq voqealar haqida gapirishib, sport bilan shug'ullanishning ajoyib tomonlari haqida hikoya qilib beradilar. Kecha yoki umumiy yig'in oxirida shahar, tuman yoki BO'SM ning kuchli jamoalari o'rtasida

ko'rgazmali o'yin o'tkazish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Bularning barchasi qatnashchilarda sport o'yinlariga katta qiziqish uyg'otadi va amaliy mashg'ulotlarni aqlan o'tkazish bu qiziqishni mustahkamlaydi.

O'quv guruhlarini tashkillab, komplektlash ko'pincha o'yin malakalarini o'rgatishda muvaffaqiyatlarga olib keladi. Bunga jidiy e'tibor berish kerak va har qanday holatda "ro'yxat bo'yicha" oddiy bo'linishga yo'l qo'yimaslik kerak, hech bo'lmaganda tarkib soni to'liq bo'lishi zarur. Agar jamoa unchalik katta bo'lmasa, ya'ni xohlovchilar soni 15-20 o'quvchini tashkil qilsa, komplektlash alog'ida mehnatni talab qilmaydi. Ammo xohlovchilar soni ko'p bo'lsa, shug'ullanuvchilarni sport o'yini bo'yicha malakalarini egallashda ularni tayyorgarligi va potentsial imkoniyatlariga qarab guruhlarga oshirish lozim. Bunda eng yaxshi ko'rsatkichga ega bo'lganlarni bir guruhga, qolganlarni boshqa guruhga birlashtirish kerak.

Tanlab olishda quyidagi ko'rsatkichlar hisobga olinadi: jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasi, o'yin texnikasini egallash qobiliyati, antropometrik ma'lumotlari, o'yinni malakalarini egallash darajasi va boshqalar.

Bizning sharoitda sport o'yinlari juda ommalashgan. Maktabda deyarli barcha o'quvchilar bu o'yinlarga qiziqishadi. Jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini aniqlash uchun nazorat sinovlarini qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi: vertikal sakrash, turgan joydan uzunlikka sakrash, tomonlari 10 va 5 m bo'lgan uchburchak bo'yicha yugurish, 1kg og'irlikdagi to'ldirma to'pni ikki qo'llab bosh orqasidan turgan joyida va sakraganda uloqtirish, voleybol setkasi orqali tennis to'pini sakrab mo'ljalga uloqtirish.

Vertikal sakrash balandligini turli usullar bilan aniqlash mumkin. Bunda sinalayotgan o'quvchining bo'yidan kelib chiqib, gavda umumiy og'irlik markazini ko'tarish balandligi hisobiga olinadi. Sakrovchanlikni aniqlash uchun asosiy usullar: tayanch joyidan mahkamlanadigan qurilmaga santimetrli lentani o'tkazish, ilib qo'yilgan lentaga yetish, unda panja uchlari bo'yicha kaftlarni boshlang'ich holati aniqlanadi – bunda yuqoriga sakrashni oxirgi nuqtasi belgilanadi; sinaluvchini holati oq qog'ozga qayd qilinadi.

Uzunlikka sakrash yumshoq tayanchga bajarilishi zarur. Yugurish bo'yicha sinov o'tkazish uchun ikkita har xil tomonlama uchburchak chiziladi: birining tomoni 10m, boshqasini 5m. Har bir burchakka to'ldirma to'p qo'yiladi. Signal bo'yicha sinalayotgan o'quvchi chap yoni bilan uchburchakka (soat strelkasiga qarama-qarshi) 30m yugurib boradi. Ikkinchi sinovda u 15m chap yon bilan yugurib boradi, bundan so'ng orqaga buriladi va yana 15m o'ng yon bilan uchburchakka qarab (soat strelkasi yo'nalishi bo'yicha) yugurib boradi.

Turgan joyida uloqtirishda sinalayotgan o'quvchi oldiga to'ldirma to'p qo'yilgan holatda o'tkaziladi. To'pni olib, orqaga egilib, bosh orqasiga ikki qo'llab to'pni olib boriladi va uni oldinga uloqtiriladi. Sakrashda to'pni uloqtirish ham xuddi shu dastlabki holatdan amalga oshiriladi.

Setka orqali tennis to'pini uloqtirish quyidagicha bajariladi: o'quvchi qo'lda to'p bilan hujum chizig'idagi 4 zonada turadi. Keyin yugurib ikkala oyoqda deysinib yuqoriga sakraydi va 6 zona turgan nishonga bir qo'llab setka orqali sakrashda to'pni uloqtiradi. Bunda setkani balandligi o'quvchini yoshi va jinsiga mos kelishi talab etiladi.

O'yin texnikasini qanday bilish qobiliyatini aniqlash uchun yo'riqchi yoki ko'rikka alohida taklif qilingan o'quvchi tomonidan ko'rsatilgan usullarni soddalashtirilgan yoki qisqartirilgan sharoitlarda o'quvchi bajarib berishi kerak. O'zini ustida yuqori uzatish va yuqoriga-to'g'riga

uzatish, pasidan va yuqoridan to'g'ri podacha, rezinaga o'rnatilgan to'plarga hujum zarba berish (5 ballik sistemada) bajariladi.

Taktika bo'yicha qobiliyatlarni o'yinlarda kuzatib aniqlanadi. Bunday kuzatishlar o'quvchini maqsadga muvofiq ravishda o'yin paytida oldin o'rganganlarini qanday bajarish va harakat malakalarini bilishga yordam beradi. O'yinda qatnashishga qarab shug'ullanuvchilarni reaksiya tezligini, epcilligini, fikrlash qobiliyatini va taktik bilimini rivojlantirish haqida ma'lumotlarga ega bo'linadi. Bu sifatlar sport o'yinlari bilan muvaffaqiyatli shug'ullanish uchun zarurdir. Bulardan tashqari turli xil topshiriqlar bilan estafetalar qo'llaniladi: turli xil dastlabki holatlardan turlicha harakatlanish usullarini bajarish, ya'ni harakatda burilishlar, to'siqlardan oshib o'tish va boshqalar. Va yana harakatli o'yinlardan ham foydalanish mumkin, bunda tezlik reaksiyasini harakatlarni almashtirish tezligi bilan qo'shib aniqlash va boshqa harakatlarni ham aniqlash mumkin: "Kecha va kunduz", "Chaqiruv", "Ovchilar va o'rdaklar", "Qo'rg'anni himoyalash", "To'p ilib oluvchiga", "To'p uchun kurash". Yakunda o'yin o'tkaziladi, barcha hoxlovchilar kuch jihatdan teng komandalarga ajratiladi. O'yinlarni kuzatish sport turining malakalarini egallash darajasini ko'rish imkoniyatini beradi. Ko'rsatilgan sinovlarda ko'rsatkichlarni yaxshi bilganlar, odatda texnik usullar va taktik harakatlarni boshqalardan ko'ra yaxshiroq bajarishi va o'yinda muvaffaqiyatli harakat qilishi ko'rinadi.

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